

SIESTA anonymisation tools

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Author	CRedit statement ⁽¹⁾
Judith Sáinz-Pardo	Writing-original draft
David Rodríguez	Writing-original draft
Mattia Mazzoli	Writing- review & editing
Víctor González	Writing - review & editing
Hans-Jürgen Wolf	Writing - review & editing
Eniafe Festus Ayetiran	Writing - review & editing
Álvaro López	Writing - review & editing

¹ CRedit (Contributor Roles Taxonomy) specifies author contribution. Choose between: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal Analysis, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Resources, Software, Supervision, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing.

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. Aim and scope of the deliverable 4

2. Introduction 4

 2.1. SIESTA’s Classification of data according to sensitiveness 5

3. Requirements’ Acquisition 5

 3.1. Use Cases 5

4. Anonymity tools for data sharing and release..... 6

 4.1. Background..... 6

 4.2 Checking anonymity levels 8

 4.2.1. User interface 10

 4.3. Anjana anonymisation tool..... 11

 4.3.1. User interface 13

 4.4. Applications to SIESTA use cases 14

5. Pseudonymity tools 15

 5.1. Background..... 15

 5.2. Selection of Tools for SIESTA 16

 5.3. Applications to SIESTA use cases 17

6. Differentially private data sharing 17

 6.1. Background..... 17

 6.1.1. Local and global differential privacy..... 17

 6.1.2. Differential privacy methods 18

 6.1.3. Frameworks analysed..... 19

 6.2. Applications to SIESTA use cases 20

7. Conclusions 21

8. References..... 22

1. AIM AND SCOPE OF THE DELIVERABLE

The objective of this report is to provide a brief summary of the activities carried out within the framework of SIESTA's Work Package 10 (WP10) including an examination of the state of the art, the selection of developed or adopted tools, and interaction with other work packages, particularly those related to use cases.

Specifically, Section 2 summarises the main objectives of WP10 and details the tiered model adopted for data sensitiveness. Then, Section 3 presents the requirements acquisition from the different use cases involved in the project.

Key milestones within this WP include the development of two software frameworks concerning data anonymisation assessment and application (namely *pyCANON* and *anjana*). These tools are presented in detail in Section 4. Further tools within the scope of this WP are related to pseudonymisation and differential privacy, and Sections 5 and 6 discuss the corresponding open source software products analysed for incorporation into the platform.

Finally, Section 7 outlines the conclusions and key results produced within WP10.

2. INTRODUCTION

In an era of increasing data-driven research, robust data privacy is paramount, particularly within sensitive domains like healthcare and social sciences. Even when data is analysed within a Trusted Research Environment (TRE), there is still a need to cater for different levels of anonymisation for different data holders and use cases.

SIESTA's WP10 addresses this critical need by focusing on the evaluation, implementation, and application of cutting-edge data de-identification techniques. Recognizing the diverse nature of research and the varying sensitivities of data, WP10 aims to develop a comprehensive strategy to accommodate a wide range of scenarios.

The objectives of WP10 were:

- Evaluate, implement and apply tools for data de-identification in collaboration with the different use cases in order to cater for their different scenarios and challenges. The data anonymisation and pseudonymisation strategy should consider different research scenarios (local, distributed and centralized).
- Implement different levels of de-identification from basic to advanced pseudonymisation and anonymisation tools.
- Develop and implement differential privacy techniques, corresponding to the different de-identification tiers and trust levels.
- Support various data reuse scenarios corresponding with the different ethical approvals obtained and sharing scenarios envisioned by the use cases.

2.1. SIESTA'S CLASSIFICATION OF DATA ACCORDING TO SENSITIVENESS

With the objective of providing safe and trusted access to sensitive data, we have developed the following tiered model for data sensitiveness:

1. Fully open data. No need to use a trusted research environment.
2. Very low risk. Pseudonymised data with very low linking risk. Unlikely to cause harm.
3. Low risk. Strongly pseudonymised datasets with some indirect identifiers.
4. Average risk. Pseudonymised personal data and confidential organisations' information.
5. High risk. Weak or no de-identification and very sensitive commercial data.
6. Very high risk. Very sensitive personal data or highly confidential government or commercial data.

SIESTA is focused on levels 2 to 5 establishing different restrictions, increasing security levels and enabling different access methods.

3. REQUIREMENTS ACQUISITION

3.1. ENGAGEMENT WITH USE CASES

To gain a deeper understanding of the SIESTA use cases and their data, and thereby evaluate the need for de-identification, we prepared a series of questions and included them in the WP6 questionnaire (see Annex I from [\[14\]](#)).

Note that as stated in the initial diagram of the WPs interaction (see [Figure 1](#), extracted from the DoA), in addition to taking advantage of the requirements gathered from WP6, WP10 will provide its tools to the use cases WPs via WP7 (SIESTA compute and storage platform). In this regard, WP10 has also followed up the activities of WP7 by attending its meetings.

Furthermore, we conducted one-on-one meetings with each of the use cases WPs (with the exception of WP16 due to its re-routing), specifically WPs 14 (epidemiology), 15 (medical imaging), 17 (text anonymisation) and 18 (demographics). In these meetings we deepen our understanding of these use cases' data, and their anonymisation needs. In addition, we learned about the tools used in their areas for de-identification tasks, and discussed the applicability of the tools being developed in WP10 (presented further down), thereby establishing ongoing collaborations for their adoption.

Figure 1: SIESTA WPs architecture and interactions. Extracted from the DoA.

4. ANONYMITY TOOLS FOR DATA SHARING AND RELEASE

4.1. BACKGROUND

The main objective of this work package is to provide users with a set of tools that allow them both to anonymise their datasets (tabular data or data that can be converted to tabular format, such as metadata), and to check the level of anonymity verified with respect to different anonymity techniques. For this purpose, we have focused on nine anonymisation techniques classically employed in the state of the art, namely: *k-anonymity*, *(α, k)-anonymity*, *l -diversity*, *entropy l -diversity*, *recursive (c, l)-diversity*, *t -closeness*, *basic β -likeness*, *enhanced β -likeness* and *δ -disclosure privacy*. Detailed definitions of these techniques can be found in [1].

In order to apply these techniques, we need first to define a set of concepts concerning the attributes in a tabular database:

- **Identifiers:** variables that allow to identify an individual unequivocally. Examples: name and surname, passport number, email, etc.

- **Quasi-identifiers:** variables that individually are not identifiers but when combined can contribute to identify an individual in the database. Examples: date of birth, gender, ZIP code, etc.
- **Sensitive attributes:** features that contain private information that must remain private and should not be extracted or associated with an individual by an attacker. Examples: salary level, illness, medical history, etc.
- **Equivalence class:** set of rows in the database that are identical with respect to the set of quasi-identifiers. To construct these equivalences in order to anonymise the data, we will usually apply hierarchies² that allow us to generalize the different variables (e.g., generalize the real value of the age to intervals of successively greater length).

The nine techniques implemented aim to prevent different types of attacks and are suitable to achieve different privacy objectives. Concerning the attacks that are mainly prevented by each technique, these are presented in Table 2 from [1]. In addition, in [2] (work elaborated within this WP), we explore in detail in which case to apply each of the nine proposed techniques depending on the purpose. This is summarized in Figure 2.

² In this context, hierarchies refer to generalizations of the original values to a new, more generic space. For example, a hierarchy on a numerical variable (e.g. age) could consist of grouping the values into intervals. The first level of the hierarchy would correspond to the more specific (smaller) intervals, and these intervals could be progressively extended in successive levels of the hierarchy. A formal definition for this concept is given in [2].

Figure 2: workflow for selecting the anonymisation technique to be applied. Extracted from [2].

4.2 CHECKING ANONYMITY LEVELS

In order to provide users with a tool that allows them to check the level of anonymity of their data, the open source Python library *pyCANON* [3] (presented in [1]) has been adopted and maintained within this work package.

With this tool, users only need to enter their dataset, the set of quasi-identifiers and the sensitive attributes (if applicable), to obtain a complete report on the nine anonymity techniques explored (in JSON, PDF or command line format), or they can obtain the individual value for each technique. In addition, in case of multiple sensitive attributes users can choose which approach they want to consider: updating or harmonization of the quasi-identifiers (see [1]).

The library can be simply installed using the command *pip install pycanon* (or *pip install pycanon[PDF]* in case you want to use the functionality for creating PDF reports). Then, in Figure 3 we show an example applied to the adult dataset [15] for getting the value of *k* for *k-anonymity* and a complete report on the privacy level in the command line:

```

from pycanon import anonymity, report

FILE_NAME = "adult.csv"
QI = ["age", "education", "occupation", "relationship", "sex", "native-country"]
SA = ["salary-class"]
DATA = pd.read_csv(FILE_NAME)

# Calculate k for k-anonymity:
k = anonymity.k_anonymity(DATA, QI)

# Print the anonymity report:
report.print_report(DATA, QI, SA)

```

Figure 3: Example of use of the pyCANON Python library. Extracted from the documentation (own elaboration).

Finally, in Figure 4 we show the output obtained for a concrete example when generating a complete anonymisation report in PDF format.

pyCANON: Check anonymity properties

Anonymity report

Apr 22 2025 10:21:42

Quasi-identifiers: ['age', 'education', 'occupation', 'relationship', 'sex', 'native-country']

Sensitive attribute(s): ['salary-class']

Anonymity technique	Value(s)
k-anonymity	k = 20
(α ,k)-anonymity	$\alpha = 1.0$ and k = 20
l-diversity	l = 1
Entropy l-diversity	l = 1
(c,l)-diversity	c = nan and l = 1
Basic β -likeness	$\beta = 2.0161490683229815$
Enhanced β -likeness	$\beta = 1.1039808747608255$
t-closeness	t = 0.6684514003294892
δ -disclosure privacy	$\delta = 2.855304953356684$

Figure 4: Example of anonymity report in PDF format.

Software details:

- GitHub repository: <https://github.com/IFCA-Advanced-Computing/pycanon>
- Current version reported in this deliverable: v1.0.5.
- Documentation: <https://pycanon.readthedocs.io/en/latest/?badge=latest>
- **Installation:** <https://pypi.org/project/pycanon/>
- CI/CD pipeline runs: <https://github.com/IFCA-Advanced-Computing/pycanon/actions/workflows/cicd.yml>
- License: Apache 2.0.

4.2.1. User interface

To integrate this tool into the platform, we will provide a user interface for this library so that the user can interact with it instead of working directly with the Python library. Then, users can upload the data that they want to check (Figure 5), select the set of quasi-identifiers and that of the sensitive attributes (Figure 6) and select the anonymity technique to be checked and whether or not to generalize in case of multiple sensitive attributes (Figure 7).

Figures 5, 6 and 7 show an initial version of the web application that was designed in this context.

Figure 5: First step of the pycanon web application (upload the data).

Figure 6: Second step of the pycanon web application (select the set of quasi-identifiers and sensitive attributes).

The screenshot shows the 'Tools | pycanon' interface. At the top, there are three progress indicators: '1 Upload the data to be checked', '2 Select the type of attributes available', and '3 Check the anonymity level'. Below these, there is a dropdown menu labeled 'Technique' and a checkbox labeled 'Generalize to the different sensitive attributes'. At the bottom right, there are 'Back' and 'Next' buttons.

Figure 7: Third step of the pycanon web application (select the technique to be checked and whether or not to generalize in case of multiple sensitive attributes).

4.3. ANJANA ANONYMISATION TOOL

On the one hand, with the *pyCANON* library users can check the level of anonymity of their data, allowing them to determine their needs in terms of generalization and hierarchies to be applied according to their privacy restrictions, detect failures in the anonymisation process previously applied, etc. On the other hand, with the *anjana* library [4] (presented in [2]) we want to provide the users with a tool that allows them to apply this anonymisation process according to the nine techniques previously mentioned.

For this, in addition to the data, the set of identifiers (to suppress them), of quasi-identifiers (to generalize them), the dictionaries with the level of hierarchies possible to apply on each quasi-identifier, the sensitive attribute, the maximum level of suppressed records and the privacy level required must be introduced. Note that the anonymisation is allowed for only one sensitive attribute, but each technique can be applied recursively for each of them in case that we deal with multiple sensitive attributes.

A use example for anonymising the adult dataset with *anjana* using (a,k) -anonymity with $k=10$ and $a=0.8$ is shown in Figure 8. Note that the other eight techniques can be applied in an analogous way using the corresponding function.

```

import pandas as pd
from anjana.anonymity import alpha_k_anonymity

data = pd.read_csv("adult.csv") # 32561 rows
data.columns = data.columns.str.strip()
cols = [
    "workclass",
    "education",
    "marital-status",
    "occupation",
    "sex",
    "native-country",
]

for col in cols:
    data[col] = data[col].str.strip()

ident = ["race"]
sens_att = "salary-class"
k = 10
alpha = 0.8
supp_level = 100

hierarchies = {
    "age": dict(pd.read_csv("hierarchies/age.csv", header=None)),
    "education": dict(pd.read_csv("hierarchies/education.csv", header=None)),
    "marital-status": dict(pd.read_csv("hierarchies/marital.csv", header=None)),
    "occupation": dict(pd.read_csv("hierarchies/occupation.csv", header=None)),
    "sex": dict(pd.read_csv("hierarchies/sex.csv", header=None)),
    "native-country": dict(pd.read_csv("hierarchies/country.csv", header=None)),
}

data_anon = alpha_k_anonymity(
    data, ident, quasi_ident, sens_att, k, alpha, supp_level, hierarchies
)

```

Figure 8: Example of using the anjana Python library. Extracted from the documentation (own elaboration).

Regarding the algorithm used to apply *k-anonymity*, as well as the other methods, we implemented a modified version of the main idea behind the datafly algorithm [13], as explained in the following. Note that we used the *pyCANON* library as an auxiliary tool to verify that the required level of anonymisation is achieved. The generalizations (introduced in the hierarchies variable) are applied following the datafly approach, based on the quasi-identifier with the highest diversity. Additionally, we have incorporated a suppression limit: if this limit is not exceeded, we allow the removal of the necessary records to achieve the desired level of anonymity. This threshold can always be set to zero to prevent any record deletion. In that case, generalizations will be applied according to the datafly approach, starting with the most diverse attribute.

Software details:

- **GitHub repository:** <https://github.com/IFCA-Advanced-Computing/anjana>
- **Current version reported in this deliverable:** *v1.1.0*.

- **Documentation:** <https://anjana.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>
- **Installation:** <https://pypi.org/project/anjana/>
- **CI/CD pipeline runs:** <https://github.com/IFCA-Advanced-Computing/anjana/actions/workflows/cicd.yml>.
- **License:** Apache 2.0.

Note that this library has been completely developed within this work package. In this line, some tutorials [5] and user guides have been provided to the different use cases. As a result, as will be explained at the end of this section, one of the use cases (epidemics - WP14) has already integrated this tool for anonymising their data belonging to one of their applications. Specifically, they used it for a use case on synthetic data generation for electronic health records, with data collected by the Italian Influenzanet platform of participatory epidemic surveillance.

4.3.1. User interface

As already detailed for the case of the *pyCANON* library we have implemented a web interface to integrate the anjana service in the platform and in order to allow users to anonymise their data in a more intuitive way. Thus, the interface allows users to upload the file with their data, and from the columns of this file to select the type of variable (identifiers, quasi-identifiers and sensitive attribute). Subsequently, it allows users to upload a csv file with the hierarchies to be applied to each quasi-identifier, and finally to select the anonymisation technique to be applied, the level of suppression, and to download the resulting anonymised file.

Some examples of the user interface developed are presented in the following figures (Figures 9, 10 and 11):

Figure 9: First step of the anonymisation process from the web application (upload the data).

Tools | Anjana

1 Upload the tabular data to anonymize — 2 Classify the attributes — 3 Select the anonymity technique to be applied and the associated parameter(s) — 4 Select the suppression limit and the hierarc...

All available techniques anonymize data by protecting the field classified as a sensitive attribute. However, the k-anonymity technique is an exception, as it focuses on preventing re-identification. For this reason, this technique does not rely on a sensitive attribute.

Technique*
alpha_k_anonymity

k*
10

Alpha*
0.8

Back Next

Figure 10: Applying (a,k)-anonymity with k=10 and a=0.8 using the web application.

Tools | Anjana

Results preview:

index	age	workclass	fnlwgt	education	education-num	marital-status	occupation	relationship	race	sex	capital-gain	capital-loss	hours-per-week	native-country	salary-class
1	[0, 80]	*	*	*	13	*	Exec-managerial	Husband	White	Male	0	0	13	United-States	<=50K
2	[0, 80]	*	*	*	9	*	Handlers-cleaners	Not-in-family	White	Male	0	0	40	United-States	<=50K
4	[0, 80]	*	*	*	13	*	Prof-specialty	Wife	Black	Female	0	0	40	Cuba	<=50K
5	[0, 80]	*	*	*	14	*	Exec-managerial	Wife	White	Female	0	0	40	United-States	<=50K
9	[0, 80]	*	*	*	18	*	Exec-managerial	Husband	White	Male	5178	0	40	United-States	>50K

Click here to download the anonymized data
adult_anonymized.csv

You can apply more anonymization methods to your processed data or use new data.

Reprocess data Process new data

Figure 11: Dataset anonymised using the web application (example).

GitHub repository (anjana-app): <https://github.com/SIESTA-eu/anjana-app>.

4.4. APPLICATIONS TO SIESTA USE CASES

Concerning the application of the two software products implemented within WP10 first task (10.1), we can highlight the use within WP14 (epidemiology use case). Specifically, Task 14.1 of WP14 collects individual health data from a participatory surveillance platform. This data is sensitive and cannot be shared as is. To enhance the data reusability and reproducibility of past studies based on these collections, WP14 tested the use of synthetic data generation for sharing electronic health records. To ensure validity in terms of privacy, both *pyCANON* and *anjana* were used.

First, multiple synthetic versions of the original dataset were generated using five different algorithms, of which two guarantee differential privacy. Next, the privacy metrics of these versions were evaluated, involving the use of *pyCANON*, for example to verify the parameters checked for *k*, *ℓ* and *t* with respect to *k-anonymity*, *ℓ-diversity* and *t-closeness*, respectively. In addition, the Anjana library was used to obtain the anonymisation levels chosen with respect to these techniques.

This example illustrates how *pyCANON* and Anjana provide an effective solution to address the challenges related to anonymisation and its verification in a practical use case. Specifically, this is reported in the preprint presented in [9]. Furthermore, this demonstrates how users can easily and intuitively incorporate these tools into their workflows, facilitating the adoption of anonymisation processes. This, along with the adoption by other external researchers (see for instance [10], [11] and [12]), allows us to confirm that the adoption of these techniques is easily feasible and achievable by different users, both within and outside the scope of SIESTA use cases.

5. PSEUDONYMITY TOOLS

5.1. BACKGROUND

Unlike anonymisation, which aims to irreversibly strip data of personal identifiers, pseudonymisation replaces direct identifiers with pseudonyms, allowing data to be processed in a less identifiable form while retaining the possibility of re-identification under specific, controlled circumstances [6].

The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), a landmark data protection law, explicitly recognizes pseudonymisation as a security measure and a means to implement data protection by design and by default. However, it should be noted that under GDPR pseudonymous data are personal data and must be processed accordingly [7].

According to the best practices stated by the European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA) [8] we can mainly distinguish three methods regarding how the pseudonymisation process is applied: deterministic, document randomization and random. In the first case, the same pseudonym will always be used for the same data independently of the database. In the case of document randomization, the same pseudonyms will be used for the same data but only within a specific database. Finally, in the case of random pseudonymisation in the same database a different pseudonym can be used for the same data.

A variety of techniques are employed to achieve pseudonymity, the choice of the tool depends on the nature of the data, the applications' requirements, the level of privacy/security expected, and the desired data utility. Some usual techniques are:

- **Counters and Random Numbers:** simply replacing an identifier with a numerical value using a counter, or just by randomly generating a number for each record. A mapping persistence mechanism is required for consistency (longitudinal studies), reversibility (when required), and avoiding collisions.
- **Hash functions:** one-way cryptographic functions that transform an input string (in this case the identifier) into a fixed length string (in this case the pseudonym). One of their characteristics is that given the same input, they always produce the same output. This consistency is a very interesting property for longitudinal studies. Possible problems are collisions (in older algorithms that are now deprecated) and attacks. To mitigate risks salted hashes (where a random value is added to the input before hashing) are commonly used.

Two main families of hash functions are used in the literature: Message digest functions (MD) and Secure hash algorithms (SHA).

- **Hash functions with authentication code:** in this case, a hash function is used together with a secret key
- **Tokenization:** Replaces sensitive data with a non-sensitive equivalent, called a token. The original data is stored securely in a "token vault," and the token is used for processing. The mapping between the token and the original data is maintained in the vault, allowing for reversible pseudonymisation.
- **Cryptographic techniques:** encryption techniques consist of applying a bidirectional function that transforms the input into a new value that can be reversed using a key. We can mainly think about two main schemes, symmetric and asymmetric
 - Symmetric encryption: a private key is used to encrypt the information and this same key is used to decrypt it.
 - Asymmetric encryption: a pair composed by a private and public key is used. The public key is used to encrypt the information and the private key is used to decrypt it.

Future developments using machine learning techniques are promising.

5.2. SELECTION OF TOOLS FOR SIESTA

In the context of the SIESTA platform, we have analysed a set of tools that can be used for data pseudonymisation. In the following, we present three libraries selected that can be integrated in the platform for this purpose:

- **hashlib:** a Python module that implements a set of secure hashes and message digest functions such as SHA256, SHA512 or MD5 among others.

GitHub: <https://github.com/python/cpython/blob/3.13/Lib/hashlib.py>.

- **hmac:** a Python module for using the HMAC method given a key and a hash algorithm.

GitHub: <https://github.com/python/cpython/blob/3.13/Lib/hmac.py>.

- **cryptography:** a Python library that implements both encryption and decryption facilities. For example, for symmetric encryption, the Fernet method can be used. For asymmetric encryption it also provides a set of algorithms such as RSA, elliptic curve or Diffie-Hellman among others. It also provides functionalities for random number generation and for hashing (including MD5 and the SHA-3 family, among others).

GitHub: <https://github.com/pyca/cryptography>.

5.3. APPLICATIONS TO SIESTA USE CASES

In the Use Case 4 (UC4), the goal is to anonymise or pseudonymise unstructured texts (in that specific UC, the texts were cyber incident reports), with the constraint that the anonymised reports can be used to train classification models as accurate as those trained with non-anonymised reports. After detecting the entities in the text prone to be anonymised, these should be anonymised or pseudonymised by means of the methods explained above.

We carried out an experiment, in which documents were manually anonymised (i.e. masking the sensitive data) or pseudonymised with tokenization or data substitution, and the performance obtained classifying the anonymised texts was comparable to the one obtained with the original texts. Therefore, the tools provided by SIESTA for pseudonymising data, combined with the tools assessed in the UC4, will be very useful.

6. DIFFERENTIALLY PRIVATE DATA SHARING

6.1. BACKGROUND

In the third task of WP10 we focus on providing users with tools to apply differential privacy to the secure sharing of their data.

Differential privacy is a mathematical definition that guarantees that an algorithm is differentially private if, when viewing its result, an outside observer cannot know whether the data of a particular individual are included in the database used to reach that result. It also ensures that, once a certain level of privacy has been established, an attacker who knows auxiliary information will not be able to break the level of privacy granted by the established privacy budget.

If we think of differential privacy for data sharing, we focus on applying mechanisms that protect data privacy while balancing its usefulness for data inference or data mining among other tasks. Specifically, we can think of two variants of differential privacy: local and global.

6.1.1. Local and global differential privacy

Let us start by giving the formal definitions for both ϵ -differential privacy and (ϵ, δ) -differential privacy.

Definition 1. ϵ -differential privacy. Let A be a randomized algorithm with domain D and range R . Be X and X' two adjacent inputs $X, X' \in D$. The following inequality applies for each $S \subseteq R$, where $\epsilon \geq 0$ is the privacy budget:

$$P[A(X) \in S] \leq e^\epsilon P[A(X') \in S].$$

We can note that a lower value of ϵ implies lower privacy and higher utility (in terms of the sanitized data more closely resembling the real data), while a higher value of ϵ implies lower privacy and higher utility.

Definition 2. (ϵ, δ) -differential privacy. *Be* A a randomized algorithm with domain D and range R . Let X and X' two adjacent inputs $X, X' \in D$. For any $S \subseteq R$ it is verified the following inequality, with $\epsilon \geq 0$ the privacy budget and $\delta \in [0,1]$ the probability of exceeding the privacy budget:

$$P[A(X) \in S] \leq e^\epsilon P[A(X') \in S] + \delta.$$

Intuitively, we can think of the two ways of applying DP. First, by local DP we mean the case in which DP mechanisms are applied on the data, before applying statistical calculation processes, visualization, queries, etc, on them. Alternatively, the most frequent approach is global DP. In this case, DP is applied on the computational processes such as statistical calculations on the data or queries on the data itself.

6.1.2. Differential privacy methods

In basic introductions to differential privacy, the coin mechanism is introduced as a preliminary intuitive idea, which works as follows:

Given a dataset, let us suppose that we want to privatize a variable of binary type (possible values YES or NO). Then, in order to do so a coin is flipped, if heads come out, the real value is assigned, while if tails comes out, a second coin is flipped. In the case of flipping the second coin, if the result is heads the value is set to YES (regardless of the actual value), otherwise it is set to NO. It is trivial to verify that according to the definition of differential privacy given in Definition 1, this mechanism verifies DP for $\epsilon = \ln(3)$.

However, in practice, mechanisms using statistical distributions are used to ensure the definition of differential privacy. For example, if we think of applying DP on statistics calculated on the data in order to share them, or on the representation of the data by means of histograms, we can consider the Laplace and Gaussian mechanisms.

To introduce these two mechanisms, let us first introduce the concepts of l_1 and l_2 -sensitivity:

Definition 3. l_1 and l_2 -sensitivity. *Be* f a function with domain D and range R , we define the l_1 -sensitivity ($\Delta_1(f)$) and the l_2 -sensitivity ($\Delta_2(f)$) as follows:

$$\Delta_1(f) = \max_{\|x-y\|_1} \|f(x) - f(y)\|_1$$

$$\Delta_2(f) = \max_{\|x-y\|_1} \|f(x) - f(y)\|_2$$

Definition 4. Laplace mechanism. *Be* f a function with domain D and range R^k $X_i \forall i \in \{1, \dots, k\}$ k i.i.d. variables from the Laplace distribution with location 0 and scale $\Delta_1(f)/\epsilon$. The Laplace mechanism M_L is defined as follows:

$$M_L(x, f, \epsilon) = f(x) + (X_1, X_2, \dots, X_k)$$

Definition 4. Gaussian mechanism. Be f a function with domain D and range R^k $X_i \forall i \in \{1, \dots, k\}$ k i.i.d variables from the Gaussian distribution with mean 0 and variation (σ^2) verifying $\sigma = \frac{A_2(f)\sqrt{2 \log(1.25/\delta)}}{\epsilon}$. The Gaussian mechanism M_G is defined as follows:

$$M_G(x, f, \epsilon, \delta) = f(x) + (X_1, X_2, \dots, X_k)$$

Note that the Laplace mechanism is used for achieving ϵ -differential privacy while the Gaussian one is used for reaching (ϵ, δ) -differential privacy. Other mechanisms can be considered, such as the Exponential one, that can be used for element selection preserving DP given a utility function. This will be further explored in WP11

These mechanisms can be used before sharing data statistics or to the queries performed on such data. Concerning local differential privacy and applying DP directly to the data before data sharing, the randomized response mechanism (or k -ary randomized response algorithm, or k -RR mechanism) can be applied:

Definition 5. Randomized response mechanism. Be D the domain of the data with k values (i.e. $D = \{x_1, \dots, x_k\}$). Be Ber the Bernoulli distribution and $b \sim Ber(k/(e^\epsilon + k - 1))$. Given $x \in D$ and the privacy budget ϵ , the randomized response mechanisms return the true value x if $b = 0$, and otherwise the value to return is sampled from D following a uniform distribution.

6.1.3. Frameworks analysed

In order to select the most suitable framework for the applying DP to the data during the ingest phase and/or the pre-processing (the application during the model development or data analytics has also been explored although it will be further elaborated as part of the WP11 activities), several open solutions were analysed. Among them, the following stand out:

- **PyDP:** it is a Python library that implements DP-versions of different statistics such as the median, mean, percentiles, etc. It uses de Laplace mechanism for providing ϵ -differential privacy guarantees.

GitHub: <https://github.com/OpenMined/PyDP>

- **Diffprivlib (IBM):** Python library dedicated to provide users with differentially private machine learning models. Different mechanisms are implemented, including the Laplace, Gaussian, Exponential and Geometric ones among others. It also provides utilities for DP-histogram visualization and differentially private calculation of statistics.

GitHub: <https://github.com/IBM/differential-privacy-library>

- **Google Differential Privacy libraries:** It composes a set of libraries for the calculation of statistics incorporating DP. For this purpose, the Laplace and Gaussian mechanisms are used, thus allowing to guarantee ϵ -DP and (ϵ, δ) -DP respectively.

GitHub: <https://github.com/google/differential-privacy>

- **OpenDP:** it is a framework built on Rust that aims to provide users with privatized versions of different statistics (e.g. variance, quantiles, etc) and histogram representations using DP. It also provides a functionality for performing differentially private PCA. It has bindings for Python and R.

GitHub: <https://github.com/opendp/opendp>

- **AutoDP:** this Python package for differential privacy implements the Gaussian mechanism for ensuring (ϵ, δ) -DP. In addition, it implements advanced techniques such as Rényi-DP, moments accountant and f-DP.

GitHub: <https://github.com/yuxiangw/autodp>

- **Opacus:** is a Python library that enables training DL PyTorch models using DP. It is built on top of PyTorch and DP can be added to training of the model using the PrivacyEngine.

GitHub: <https://github.com/pytorch/opacus>

- **TensorFlow Privacy:** is a Python library that provides users with optimizers that include differential privacy for training TensorFlow based models. This library allows training DL models including DP during the gradient descent process, by introducing a clipping norm for the gradient and a noise scaling factor. The most commonly used Tensorflow optimizers are included in its privatized version, including Adam, Adagrad and SGD.

GitHub: <https://github.com/tensorflow/privacy>

However, we have to take into account that some of these frameworks are expected to be used for both local and global application on data, queries or histogram visualization (e.g. PyDP, OpenDP, AutoDP, Diffprivlib and Google Differential Privacy), while others are intended to be used within a ML/DL model training (e.g. Opacus and TensorFlow Privacy).

6.2. APPLICATIONS TO SIESTA USE CASES

Specifically, in the context of WP15 (medical imaging use case), PyDP has been used to apply DP to the calculation of different statistics related to WP15 use case 1. This has been done by integrating this library in a Python pipeline for analysing tabular data belonging to this use case. Concerning the mechanisms, the Laplacian one has been used in order to get the bounded mean for different values of the privacy budget (ϵ).

7. CONCLUSIONS

The protection of data privacy and confidentiality is paramount for many data-intensive applications. However, this must be achieved while preserving the data utility necessary to achieve those applications' objectives.

In the context of TREs, such as those being developed for SIESTA, it might still be required to apply different levels of protection depending on the sensitivity of the data, the trust between the data providers and the scientist analysing the data inside the TREs, legal issues or other circumstances. As a consequence, in WP10 we have explored the state of the art, examined existing tools, and developed new ones to address these diverse needs.

We have focused on the SIESTA use cases, and established a collaboration with them, but not closing the door to other possible requirements from future users.

Following the tasks' organisation we have:

- Adopted the *pyCANON* tool to assess dataset anonymity levels and helped use cases to use it.
- Developed the *anjana* tool that provides a selection of different anonymisation techniques.
- Collaborated with the use case's WPs to help them adopt the tools, and support them if they have special needs.
- Examine the pseudonymity techniques, and provide an assortment of tools that can be used for different needs.
- Explored the uses of differential privacy and support use cases in its application.

With the availability of these different types of tools, while leaving the door open for specific user requirements, WP10 is in a position to help applications with very diverse privacy requirements to adopt the SIESTA platform for the analysis of their sensitive data.

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